

**LINGUISTIC CAPITAL, ENGLISH PRESTIGE, AND
ACADEMIC SUCCESS: A COMPARATIVE
SOCIOLINGUISTICS STUDY OF STUDENTS IN
PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTOR
UNIVERSITIES OF PAKISTAN**

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Abstract

This study explored the association of linguistic capital, prestige attached to English and academic achievement of students studying in some universities of public and private sector in Punjab, Pakistan. The study used quantitative comparative research design and was guided by the theory of Linguistic Capital by Bourdieu. The data was gathered from 400 undergraduate and post graduate students who were selected from four public universities and four private universities through structured questionnaire. Descriptive data was used to analyze the data with SPSS using Cronbach's alpha, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and Independent Samples t-test. The results indicated strong positive correlations between linguistic capital, English prestige and academic achievement. Additionally, the students of the private universities had significantly more linguistic capital, more prestige of English and more academic achievement than their peers in public universities. The study finally concludes that English is a useful tool for educational attainment and recommends to make educational opportunities equal and equitable by improving the programmes of English language support in higher educational institutions in Pakistan.

Keywords: *Academic Success, English Prestige, Higher Education, Linguistic Capital, Pakistan, Public and Private Universities.*

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1. Introduction

Language is not just a means of communication; it is also a powerful social resource which affects access to education, career progression and social mobility. In multilingual societies, there is a prestige associated with a language that confers academic and economic opportunities to people. English is a special language in Pakistan, as it is used in higher education, government and for international communication. Urdu is the national language and some regional languages are also in use but English still represents high standards of education, social status and employability. Proficiency in English is therefore now a form of linguistic capital which carries with it important academic and social benefits for the students. Language resource differentials add to the inequities in the educational attainment of university students in various linguistic, institutional, and socioeconomic settings (Bourdieu, 1991; Rahman, 2022).

Pierre Bourdieu introduced the term 'linguistic capital', and defined language as a symbolic resource by which people gain power, prestige and social recognition. Speakers with the dominant language variety have better opportunities in education and career, as education institutions favour language practices from the socially privileged classes (Bourdieu, 1991). In countries where English is the language used in higher education and to get a good job, students who speak English well are more likely to do well in school and to find a job in the competitive marketplace. So, linguistic capital is now inextricably linked with education outcomes and social mobility, instead of only being a measure of language competence (Bourdieu, 1991; Grenfell, 2014).

Pakistan is a good case to study the relationship between linguistic capital and educational inequality as there are significant differences between public and private universities. English-based instruction, international programmes, online teaching materials and plenty of communication skills training are most prominent features of private universities. Public universities, although academically sound, have a wider clientele of students from diverse language and socio-economic backgrounds, many of whom have passed previous exams in Urdu or language other than Urdu. The differences in institutions provide different chances for students to gain and use English as linguistic capital which would affect their academic achievement and potential career (Rahman, 2022; Higher Education Commission, 2024).

English has become more and more symbolic in Pakistani society due to its connection with high socioeconomic class, competitiveness and postings to elite professions. Even though students may not be academically strong, their lack of English proficiency often leads to them being seen as less intelligent, less competent, and less professionally prepared. This perception impacts on classroom participation, teacher expectations, peer interactions, scholarship opportunities and employability upon graduation. As a result, English is not just a mark of linguistic ability, but is also a signifier

of social status, influencing educational and institutional disparities. The studies have reflected that students tend to think that possessing English is a sign of confidence, leadership and professional success in Pakistani higher education system, which reflects its prestigious position as a resource language in higher education sector (Mahboob, 2020; Shamim & Rashid, 2019).

Poverty, early educational experiences, institutional resources and support, motivation, and foreign language proficiency are all related to academic achievement in university settings. Of all of these, English proficiency has proved to be a very important factor as most of the university textbooks, research articles and examination papers are in English and most of the interaction in classroom is in English. Students whose English is not strong may find it challenging to understand academic content and to engage in academic discussion, writing, and accessing academic literature from outside the country. In contrast, children with higher levels of linguistic capital will tend to be more successful academically, have more effective research skills, and engage in classroom activities with more confidence. Hence, the study should include the investigation of linguistic capital in addition to English prestige for a complete examination of academic achievement in Pakistani universities (Coleman, 2011; Macaro et al., 2018).

Though English is now regarded as an educational tool, in empirical studies in Pakistan, the researchers have concentrated on either the methodology of English language teaching or the students' language attitudes or policy in English language. Fewer studies using Bourdieu's sociological approach have explored English using a combined lens of linguistic capital and the prestige of English and their combined effects on academic outcomes in different types of university. Additionally, current studies often focus on individual institutions or on smaller geographic scales and do not allow for widespread conclusions regarding the higher education sector in Pakistan. Even though higher education institutions have become increasingly diverse in recent decades (the last twenty years) (Rahman, 2022; Shamim, 2017), comparative evidence is still very scarce.

The present study aims at filling this void by comparing the students attending four private universities (The University of Lahore, Minhaj University Lahore, University of Central Punjab and Lahore University of Management Sciences) with students of four public universities (University of the Punjab, University of Education, University of Sargodha and University of Sahiwal). The selected universities are representative of the different institutional contexts and admission criteria, their teaching methods and their student population, as well as their language environments. The cross-institutional comparison allows a more detailed examination of the relationship between linguistic capital and the prestige of the English language and its role in successful academic attainment in different educational settings.

Finally, this study adds to the sociolinguistic and educational research by combining the Bourdieu's theory of linguistic capital with the notion of English prestige in the higher education of Pakistan. The study aims at providing evidence that will guide language policy, curriculum planning, and equitable educational practices through exploring the difference between public and private university students in terms of their linguistic capital and academic performance. The results are anticipated to help inform policy makers, university managers and teachers in developing policies to mitigate the linguistic inequities that uphold equal academic opportunities for students from diverse linguistic and socioeconomic backgrounds (Bourdieu, 1991; Macaro et al., 2018; Rahman, 2022).

1.1. Problem Statement

Although English has gained increasing relevance as a means of linguistic capital in higher education system in Pakistan, little empirical research has focused on the interaction of linguistic capital and the prestige of English on students' academic performance in public and private Universities. Although previous research has mainly concentrated on the role of English in language teaching, language policy or learners' attitudes toward English, comparatively little research has been devoted to the sociological role of English as a symbolic resource, generating educational advantages and inequalities. Furthermore, comparative evidence of pupils from public and private universities is still limited, and there is a lack of knowledge regarding how pupils' linguistic capital, perceptions of English prestige and academic achievement are shaped by their institutional environments. To fill this gap, a study is conducted to compare the students' linguistic capital, English prestige, and their academic success from four public and four private universities of Punjab, Pakistan in light of Bourdieu's Theory of Linguistic Capital (Bourdieu, 1991; Rahman, 2022; Shamim, 2017).

1.2. Research Objectives

- a) To examine the relationship between linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success among students in selected public and private sector universities of Pakistan.
- b) To compare the levels of linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success between students enrolled in selected public and private sector universities of Pakistan.

1.3. Research Questions

- a) What is the relationship between linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success among students in selected public and private sector universities of Pakistan?
- b) How do students from selected public and private sector universities differ in terms of linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success?

1.4. Significance of The Study

The importance of this study lies in the extension of the application of the Theory of Linguistic Capital in the context of higher education in Pakistan where English still enjoys high prestige, achievement, and socioeconomic mobility. The study looks at the relationship between linguistic capital, English prestige and academic achievement, and as such is part of the expanding sociolinguistic literature, which considers language a social asset rather than just a means of communication. The results of the findings will enhance theoretical discussions on language inequality as this is a live issue in Pakistani universities where multilingualism and language inequalities are significant (Bourdieu, 1991; Grenfell, 2014).

The study is of particular value for higher education policy makers and university administrators as well. Knowing the sign of the impact of linguistic capital on students' academic performance aids universities in designing language support programmes, academic writing centres and language enhancement programmes to mitigate learning inequalities. The findings can also help the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan and the university administration to devise a policy which ensures equal chances of learning for any student who speaks a different language regardless of his or her socio-economic status, as well as equal chances for those who are more proficient in English to excel (Higher Education Commission Pakistan, 2024; Rahman, 2022).

In addition, the comparative design that included four public and four private universities provided useful insights into the institutional differences in language practices and educational outcomes. In the realm of curriculum development, education planners, ELT, and English teachers may benefit from the study to gain insights into students' motivation, classroom involvement, and learning outcomes due to the prestige of English. It also lays a groundwork for the future studies in the field of linguistic inequality, language policy, and educational equity in multilingual societies in general and in the South Asian higher education contexts, in particular (Shamim, 2017; Macaro et al., 2018).

1.5. Limitations of The Study

This study focuses on the undergraduate and postgraduate students from eight Universities of Punjab, Pakistan. Thus, the results may not be applicable to all public and private universities in the country. Furthermore, the study is based on self-reports, through questionnaires, that can be affected by the perception of the participants and by response bias. Lastly, the study only covers linguistic capital, English prestige and academic success, leaving out factors like socioeconomic status, parental education, learning motivation and institutional facilities as irrelevant to the study.

1.6. Delimitations of The Study

The study is limited to four private universities (The University of Lahore, Minhaj University Lahore, University of Central Punjab and Lahore University of Management

Sciences) and four public universities (University of the Punjab, University of Education Lahore, University of Sargodha and University of Sahiwal). It takes a narrow scope that looks only at the students studying at these institutions and only at the three dominant factors, namely, linguistic capital, prestige of English, and academic achievement. This study is carried out using quantitative comparative research design and only examines the aspect of language learning, language teaching methods and institutional language policy as related to Bourdieu's Theory of Linguistic Capital and does not examine other aspects of the language learning and teaching process or any other language policy.

2. Literature Review

The term linguistic capital has emerged as one of the most influential approaches in sociolinguistics and educational research to the study of the role of language as a resource which affects educational opportunities and social mobility. The sociological approach to language is not only seen as an instrument to communicate, but it is also regarded as a symbolic power which can have a social advantage or disadvantage in the situations it is used. In multilingual societies like Pakistan, English is accorded a privileged status since it is strongly linked with higher education, government administration, professional jobs, and international communication. Hence, students with good command of English have better academic prospects and social acceptability than students who are taught through Urdu or regional languages. The inequitable distribution of linguistic resources has been a topic of growing scholarly interest in research on educational inequality and language policy (Bourdieu, 1991; Grenfell, 2014).

The term "linguistic capital" was coined by Pierre Bourdieu, in his general theory of cultural capital and symbolic power. Bourdieu (1991) argues that language is not neutral but has different values or dimensions and the symbolic values of the language and language variation vary from one social and institutional setting to another. Dominant language is recognized and rewarded at educational institutions, giving an advantage to those who already have competence in the dominant language. Linguistic capital is thus acquired through one's family environment, education, and social contacts, and is then turned into educational outcomes, career success and social status. He also claimed that, despite the attention often given to the role of language in the classroom, schools actually have an unconsciously reproducing effect on the existing social inequalities since they privilege the language of the social elites and marginalize the language of less privileged groups.

Linguistic capital - and its connections to education - have been examined in a range of educational contexts. Students with more control over the dominant academic language have been shown repeatedly to have higher levels of classroom participation, academic writing, critical reading and exam success. Since the assessment of students is mainly carried out through their language, the latter with higher language capital tend to

be more confident with their educational results. Grenfell (2014) highlighted that educational achievement is not just a matter of students' cognitive skills, but also of their capacity to apply the language practices which are preferred in educational context. Linguistic capital is thus a hidden force that perpetuates educational inequalities from generation to generation.

In the Pakistani context despite a multilingual linguistic context, English is the major linguistic capital in higher education. Urdu is the national language in Pakistan and there are still many other regional languages like Punjabi, Sindhi, Pashto, Balochi and Saraiki which are the primary languages of communication in Pakistan. However, English is the language of higher education, competitive exams, court and international communications. This privileged status has made English an important marker of educational status and socioeconomic mobility as claimed by Rahman (2022). The unequal distribution of linguistic capital between education sectors results in English medium students having better academic benefits than Urdu-medium students.

With the globalization of the world English is becoming more and more important. The need for English proficiency has been reinforced by internationalisation in higher education, technological advances and the global labour market. Countries are becoming more and more dependent on English as the language of science, technology, business, and international scholarship, according to Coleman (2011). International literature, publishing research and communication in English are now expectations of universities for students. As a result, English has been transformed from a language asset to a knowledge network asset and as a result, language has also become an employment asset.

The socio-cultural prestige of English has been manifested, and it has created certain shifts within the public and private higher education institutions in Pakistan. Private universities typically offer more opportunities to teach in English, to interact with students, to have foreign curricula, and to develop communication skills. Public Universities, on the other hand, are more likely to admit students from a wider spectrum of educational and socioeconomic backgrounds, many of whom have done their secondary and higher education in Urdu or regional languages. These differences between institutions can impact the chances students have to access linguistic capital and gain from the symbolic capital of English. Shamim (2017) posits that inequitable access to English education leads to educational inequity since students entering universities have different levels of language competence, confidence, and readiness.

English prestige is not just about students' academic ability but also affects students' identity, confidence and social interaction. English skills in Pakistan are often linked with intelligence, professionalism, leadership and even a higher socioeconomic status, as stated by Mahboob (2020). When students speak English fluently, they are typically seen as more capable and competent by teachers and others. These perceptions

can have a positive impact on participation in class, opportunities to participate in leadership roles, selection of scholarships, and employment following graduation. Thus, the prestige of English is a crucial sociolinguistic aspect that can affect students' learning experience, in addition to their linguistic skills.

More recent empirical research has also confirmed the connection between linguistic capital and educational performance. In their extensive literature review on EMI, Macaro et al. (2018) found that the students who are more proficient in English tend to be more academically engaged, better understand the content of the subject, and perform well in the overall education. The same has been found to be true of language proficiency in multilingual education environments: language proficiency is a key that opens the door to academic resources, critical thinking, collaborative learning, and research productivity. The results of this study corroborate Bourdieu's claims about the power of linguistic capital as a valuable educational asset that can lead to enduring benefits in the academic and professional contexts.

While the significance of English proficiency in education has been documented in the past, there have been few studies that have looked at the relationships between linguistic capital, the prestige of English and student achievement in the context of higher education in Pakistan. The majority of the studies in Pakistan have focused on the study of language policy, English language teaching, and attitudes of the students towards English; however, there are very few studies that have examined the role of English as symbolic capital and how it generates educational inequalities in various institutional contexts. The gap created is the basis for the present study which comparatively investigates students of selected public and private universities to explore the impact of linguistic capital and prestige of English in gaining academic success in the context of Pakistani higher education system.

The status of English has turned into one of the salient features of higher education curriculum frameworks in many postcolonial societies. Language prestige is the social value and status granted to a language by a community which may affect educational, employment, and social mobility. English proficiency is often considered a sign of intelligence, competence and socioeconomic status in countries where English is used in higher education and as a language of professional communication. Such a symbolic value turns English into social capital, which gives people access to education and professional opportunities denied to them if they are not native speakers. Bourdieu (1991) stated that dominant language prestige is socially constructed and institutionally maintained; that is, one who has the preferred language variety has symbolic and material advantages.

The prestige of English has been enhanced by the process of globalization, which has made it the language of international education, research, science, business and technology. According to Crystal (2019), English has become a language of the world to

communicate people who are different in language and culture. With the growth of inter-university cooperation and academic exchange programs, English has become an indispensable tool for gaining access to academic literature, for publishing research work and for competing on international job markets. For these reasons, students may see English as a subject that not only serves a purpose in school but also as a viable asset that will profit them in their future endeavors in school and in life (Coleman, 2011). This perception instills a positive attitude among learners towards acquiring English as a means to unlock their upward mobility.

English has a unique role as a sociolinguistic entity in Pakistan where it is an official language, the language of higher education and a language of higher status jobs. Rahman (2022) pointed out that the past history of colonial education and the present day of globalization have reinforced the symbolic nature and power of English as a marker of educational privilege and socioeconomic status. A student who has studied English-medium education has access to higher education, competitive exams, multinational jobs and international scholarships and fellowships, where he enjoys higher status. On the other hand, students who have studied mostly in Urdu or regional languages are often faced with language stereotypes when they step into universities where English is being used as a medium of instruction and assessment in the classrooms. The differences reflect the way in which language acts as a means of perpetuating educational inequity.

A literature search of the research on language attitudes reveals that in the eyes of university students, English is modern, professional, confident and intellectual. According to Mahboob (2020), the students of Pakistan sometimes consider English as a necessity to excel in the academics and in their career. Such attitudes affect learners' language learning motivation and also help to strengthen the prestige hierarchy of English and indigenous language. Positive attitudes towards English are considered a reinforcement factor of language learning, but can also cause the student to feel insecure in the language in the case of students with limited English proficiency. This imbalance reflects the intricate connection between language prestige, identity and involvement in education in multilingual society.

Academic success is a multi-faceted phenomenon, defined from students' achievement, learning outcomes, classroom engagement, critical thinking to their overall learning development. Current research in education acknowledges that achievement is a function of cognitive, social, institutional, and linguistic factors, along with intelligence. Language proficiency is one of the best predictors for university success among these variables, as students should be able to listen to lectures, understand academic texts, complete written assignments, and express themselves in academic settings. Students with higher ELS skills tend to achieve higher levels of academic engagement, understand

disciplinary content better, and perform better in learning, especially in schools that teach in English (Macaro et al., 2018).

There are also several international studies that have been published that have documented the relationship between English proficiency and academic achievement. Cummins (2000) asserted that knowledge of language will have significant impact on the learners' ability to process academic content, solve complex problems, and develop higher order thinking skills. Academically linguistically proficient students are better able to engage in collaborative learning, to articulate academic writing, and to understand research-based knowledge. Likewise, Schleppegrell (2004) pointed out that students' ability to master academic language allows them to interact with their subjects' discourse or language in a way that benefits their learning and their confidence in learning. The results indicate that the linguistic competence has a direct role in students' academic development and is not just a communicative ability.

The need for English proficiency in Higher Education has been also noted by the Pakistani scholars. Shamim (2017) noted that many of the students joining public universities face significant problems as they move from Urdu medium and regional language education to the English-medium system of education. Often such language transitions lead to decreased participation in class, heightened exam anxiety and poor exam performance. Students with educational backgrounds in the English medium, on the contrary, are more easily able to adjust to the university environment, as they have experience with the academic environment in English. These differences in institutional structures reinforce Bourdieu's main point that institutions are reinforcing the privileges of those who have already acquired the dominant linguistic capital.

Students' self-confidence and eagerness to speak English is also an aspect of linguistic capital that is relevant to academic achievement. The competence in language has an impact on the learners' self-efficacy, interaction in the classroom, and class participation in academic discussion. Students who feel they are competent English speakers will be more likely to ask questions, join in seminars, present research or work collaboratively with others. On the other hand, students with weak English skills tend to shy away from participating in the classroom for fear of making mistakes. According to Bandura (1997), self-efficacy beliefs play an important role in academic behaviors, and linguistic confidence has an indirect impact on academic success as it influences academic involvement. Hence, the prestige of English may be a determinant of academic achievement beyond language skills, in terms of student's self-perceptions of competence and confidence.

While a great deal of literature exists on the relation between linguistic capital and academic success globally, empirical research which considers the role of linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success in Pakistani higher education is scarce.

Previous Pakistani studies have focused mainly on methods in English language teaching, language policy, bilingual education, or attitudes of students towards English, with limited attention paid to the understanding of the English language as a means of symbolic capital which influences educational opportunities in the various institutional settings. Moreover, the evidence compared between public and private universities is still limited, and despite the differences of educational background, language exposure, and resources of the students, there are still some similarities. This gap needs to be addressed for the understanding of the role of linguistic capital in educational inequalities and achievement in an evolving education system in Pakistan. The present study hence builds on the previous research by making a comparative analysis between students from selected public and private universities with the objective of finding out the impact of linguistic capital and the prestige of English on the academic success of the students, by using the theoretical frame of Bourdieu sociology of language.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The present study used quantitative comparative research design to compare the relationship of linguistic capital, English prestige and academic success of the university students of Pakistan. The data were collected from the students of selected universities in the public sector by using the method of cross-sectional survey. The comparative design allowed the researcher to explore the similarities and differences of the two university sectors and also explore relationships between the study variables. The choice of this design was deemed suitable as it allows for statistical comparison and empirical evidence of the different linguistic capital and English prestige and academic achievement in different institutional settings (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

3.2. Population of The Study

The study targeted the students of undergraduate and postgraduate level from eight universities of Punjab, Pakistan. The selected private universities were The University of Lahore, Minhaj University Lahore, University of Central Punjab and Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS) while the selected public universities were University of the Punjab Lahore, University of Education Lahore, University of Sargodha, and University of Sahiwal. The universities were chosen because they reflect various types of institutional contexts and are suitable for comparing students' linguistic capital, perceptions of the prestige of English and academic achievement.

3.3. Sample and Sampling Technique

Eight universities were selected and 50 students from each university were taken to ensure uniformity of representation of the Public and Private sector universities. Stratified random sampling was used for selection of participants, which involved dividing students based on their university and then sampling them from each university. This

sampling technique provided equal proportion of both sectors of universities and ensured the reliability and generalizability of the findings among the selected universities (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

3.4. Research Instrument

The data was obtained using a structured questionnaire which had four parts. The initial section collected the demographic data regarding gender, age, degree program, and type of university. The rest of the items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree) to reflect the presence of Linguistic Capital, English Prestige and Academic Success. The items of the questionnaire were modified based on previously validated questionnaires, suitable for the context of higher education in Pakistan. The instrument was pretested by experts in the field of applied linguistics to establish content validity and piloted to establish the reliability of the instrument before data collection was taken.

3.5. Data Collection Procedure

Following the consent of administration of selected Universities, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the students in regular academic sessions. They were briefed on the study, made aware of the confidentiality of the answers and told that the participation was voluntary. Questionnaires were retrieved immediately after completed to ensure high response rate and very few missing data. The anonymity, informed consent and voluntary participation principles were carefully followed during collection of data.

4. Data Analysis

The data thus gathered were analyzed statistically using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 29. To summarise participants' demographic characteristics and responses, descriptive statistics were computed, such as frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations. To explore the relationship between linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success for the first research question, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was used. To answer the second research question, Independent Samples t-test were employed to compare the students from public and private universities. The results were presented in tables with appropriate interpretations and statistical significance was set at 0.05 level, which is considered significant.

5. Data Analysis and Results

The analysis of the collected data from 400 students of four public and four private universities of Punjab, Pakistan is presented in this section. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 29 was used for data analysis. Demographic characteristics of the respondents and the study variables were summarized using descriptive statistics. The reliability of the research instrument was obtained by calculating Cronbach's alpha. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was used to analyse the

relationship between linguistic capital, prestige of the English language and academic success and Independent Samples t-test was applied to compare students from public and private universities. The results are reported based on the research purposes and research questions.

5.1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	194	48.5
Female	206	51.5
Total	400	100.0

Table 4.1 shows the gender distribution of the respondents. Out of the total sample of 400 students, 194 (48.5%) were male, whereas 206 (51.5%) were female. A slight majority of respondents were female, suggesting a balanced representation of both genders, which will help to diversify and strengthen the data gathered.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
18–20 Years	95	23.8
21–23 Years	195	48.8
24–26 Years	70	17.5
Above 26 Years	40	10.0
Total	400	100.0

Table 4.2 shows the age distribution of the respondents. Nearly half (48.8%) of the participants were aged 21-23 years and 23.8% were aged 18-20. 17.5% of the students were in the age group of 24-26 years, and 10% were more than 26 years. Based on these findings it can be concluded that the students consist mainly of traditional-age university students.

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents by Degree Programme

Degree Programme	Frequency	Percentage
BS	246	61.5
MA/MSc	76	19.0
MPhil	54	13.5
PhD	24	6.0
Total	400	100.0

As shown in the table 4.3, a majority of the respondent (61.5%) were pursuing BS programmes. For students pursuing MA/MSc degrees, 19% were found and for those pursuing MPhil and PhD degrees, 13.5% and 6% respectively were found. This distribution is due to the fact that the selected universities have more undergraduate students.

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents by University Sector

University Sector	Frequency	Percentage
Private Universities	200	50.0
Public Universities	200	50.0
Total	400	100.0

Table 4.4 shows that there were an equal number of respondents from both sectors in the study. 50% of the students (200 students) were drawn from private universities, and the other half (200 students) were drawn from public universities. It brings the balanced representation from both the public and private universities to allow the comparison between the public and private universities to be carried out without bias.

5.2. Reliability Analysis

The internal consistency of the questionnaire was tested by reliability analysis with Cronbach's Alpha. Taber, 2018, suggests that a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.70 or higher is acceptable for social science research.

Table 5 Reliability Statistics

Variable	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Linguistic Capital	8	0.83
English Prestige	8	0.86
Academic Success	8	0.84
Overall Instrument	24	0.89

The reliability coefficients of the research instrument are shown in Table 4.5. The Cronbach's Alpha of the items ranged between 0.83 and 0.86 and the reliability coefficient for the entire instrument was 0.89. The values reflect a high degree of internal consistency among the questionnaire items, indicating the reliability of the questionnaire for the measurement of linguistic capital, English prestige and academic success.

Statement-wise Analysis of Linguistic Capital

In order to meet the first research objective, descriptive statistics were used to analyze the respondents perception on linguistic capital. To determine the level of agreement among the participants, mean scores and standard deviations were calculated for the statements.

Table 6 Statement-wise Analysis of Linguistic Capital

Item	Statement	Mean	SD
LC1	I can communicate effectively in English during classroom discussions.	3.91	0.82
LC2	I am confident while speaking English with teachers.	3.87	0.86
LC3	I can easily understand English academic texts.	3.94	0.79
LC4	I regularly use English while completing academic assignments.	4.02	0.77
LC5	My English language skills help me perform better in university.	4.08	0.73
LC6	I actively participate in English-based classroom activities.	3.82	0.84

LC7	I have received sufficient English language exposure before entering university.	3.79	0.89
LC8	My English proficiency gives me confidence in academic settings.	4.01	0.75

All the respondents had positive perceptions of their linguistic capital, as shown in Table 4.6. The strongest mean score ($M = 4.08$) was given to the statement "My English language skills help me to perform better in university", which suggests that students strongly believed that their English language skills were beneficial to their academic performance. The lowest mean ($M = 3.79$) was related to English language exposure before university, indicating that students had different linguistic backgrounds when entering university. Generally, the results show that the respondents had relatively high linguistic capital, thus emphasizing the role of English in higher education.

5.3. Statement-wise Analysis of English Prestige

English Prestige is the second construct that was studied in this research. Students' perceptions of the social, educational and professional values of English were evaluated by eight statements. To assess the level of agreement of respondents with the statements, mean scores and standard deviations were computed.

Table 7 Statement-wise Analysis of English Prestige (N = 400)

Item	Statement	Mean	SD
EP1	English is the language of academic success in Pakistan.	4.21	0.68
EP2	Students who speak English fluently receive greater respect.	4.16	0.72
EP3	English proficiency increases employment opportunities.	4.34	0.61
EP4	Using English improves a person's social status.	4.08	0.76
EP5	Most successful professionals communicate effectively in English.	4.26	0.65
EP6	English is essential for higher education.	4.39	0.57
EP7	I feel motivated to improve my English because of its prestige.	4.12	0.71
EP8	Society values English speakers more than speakers of local languages.	3.96	0.84

As shown in Table 4.7, the respondents' attitudes towards the prestige of English were very positive. The highest mean score ($M = 4.39$, $SD = 0.57$) was obtained for the statement "English is important for higher education", indicating that there was a high level of agreement among the students on the importance of English in higher education. Likewise, students were very positive about how English proficiency improves chances of employment ($M = 4.34$) and how effective communication in English is a characteristic of successful professionals ($M = 4.26$). The statement that society values the English language speaker over the local language speaker was the smallest mean score ($M = 3.96$) but respondents did confirm that they believed that. In general, the results indicated that students have high self-assessment of English as a prestigious language which can help

students achieve good academic performance, succeed in their jobs, and be recognized socially.

5.4. Statement-wise Analysis of Academic Success

Academic Success was the third variable of the study. Students' perceptions of their academic performance, classroom participation and learning experiences were measured by eight questionnaire items. The level of academic success of the respondents was determined using descriptive statistics.

Table 8 Statement-wise Analysis of Academic Success (N = 400)

Item	Statement	Mean	SD
AS1	I achieve good academic grades in my university courses.	3.94	0.78
AS2	I actively participate in classroom discussions.	3.88	0.81
AS3	I can complete English-medium assignments successfully.	4.02	0.73
AS4	I understand lectures delivered in English without difficulty.	3.97	0.77
AS5	I perform well in written examinations.	3.91	0.79
AS6	I can easily access and understand international research articles.	3.84	0.83
AS7	My English proficiency contributes to my academic achievement.	4.15	0.69
AS8	Overall, I consider myself academically successful.	4.01	0.74

Table 4.8 shows that the respondents had positive perception of their academic achievement. The most positive mean score ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.69$) was for the statement "My English proficiency helps my achievement in school," showing that students acknowledged that their English proficiency is an important aspect of their school achievement. High mean scores also were reported for completing assignments in English ($M = 4.02$) and total academic performance ($M = 4.01$). The comparatively low mean score ($M = 3.84$) was for understanding international research articles, indicating that some students still face difficulties when reading more advanced academic texts. Overall, the findings show that the respondents are fairly successful academically.

5.5. Overall Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were calculated to explore overall level of each of the three study variables.

Table 9 Overall Descriptive Statistics of the Study Variables

Variable	Mean	SD	Level
Linguistic Capital	3.93	0.81	High
English Prestige	4.19	0.69	High
Academic Success	3.97	0.77	High

The overall descriptive statistics for the three variables are given in Table 4.9. The students had the highest mean score for English Prestige ($M = 4.19$), meaning that English was seen by the students as a prestigious language that is linked to academic and professional achievement. The mean of Academic Success was 3.97 and a mean of 3.93 for Linguistic Capital, indicating respondents' high levels of English-related linguistic

capital and positive academic outcomes. These results offer initial insights into the importance of English in students' academic life in Pakistani universities.

5.6. Link with Research Objective 1

The descriptive data shows that the students in general have high linguistic capital and the students have a positive attitude towards English as a prestigious language which helps in their learning process. The findings of these analyses offer preliminary insight into the relationship between linguistic capital, English prestige, and school achievement and are consistent with the goal of Research Objective 1 to explore the relationship between linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic achievement. To provide the empirical evidence, however, descriptive statistics are not sufficient to establish relationships among variables; hence Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis is carried out in the next section.

5.7. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis

To address **Research Objective 1**, "*To examine the relationship between linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success among students in selected public and private sector universities of Pakistan,*" a **Pearson Product-Moment Correlation** analysis was performed. This statistical test was used to determine the direction and strength of the relationships among the three study variables.

Table 10 Pearson Correlation Analysis among Linguistic Capital, English Prestige, and Academic Success (N = 400)

Variables	1	2	3
1. Linguistic Capital	1		
2. English Prestige	.682**	1	
3. Academic Success	.714**	.653**	1

Note. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation coefficients among the three study variables are shown in Table 4.10. The results showed that there is a strong positive and statistically significant relationship between Linguistic Capital and English Prestige ($r = .682, p < .001$) which means that the more the students have in terms of Linguistic Capital, the higher their perception of English is as a language of prestige. In the same way, the students with high English language resources reported higher Academic Success scores, with high positive correlation ($r = .714, p < .001$) between Linguistic Capital and Academic Success.

The results also show that Academic Success and English Prestige are highly correlated ($r = .653, p < .001$). This suggests that an increase in the educational and social importance of English is linked to higher academic outcomes. The correlation coefficients were all positive and statistically significant, thus indicating that all three variables were closely related to each other.

5.8. Link with Research Objective 1

The first research objective, which was to investigate the relationship between the three variables, namely linguistic capital, English prestige and academic success, is directly addressed in the correlation analysis. All three variables were found to be significantly positively related, suggesting that linguistic capital and the prestige of the English language are factors that are important in relation to students' academic performance in higher education.

6. Answer to Research Question 1

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success among students in selected public and private sector universities of Pakistan?*

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis support the conclusions that linguistic capital is positively related to both English prestige and academic outcomes, and that English prestige is positively related to academic outcomes. Hence, the answer to the Research Question 1 is that there are significant positive correlations among the three variables.

6.1. Independent Samples *t*-Test

For the purpose of answering Research Objective 2 "To compare the level of linguistic capital, English prestige and academic success between students enrolled in selected public and private sector universities of Pakistan", Independent Samples *t*-test was used. This test was conducted to test for the existence of statistically significant difference between the students of public and private universities.

Table 11 Comparison of Public and Private University Students

Variable	University Sector	Mean	SD	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Linguistic Capital	Private	4.18	0.51	8.42	.000
	Public	3.68	0.56		
English Prestige	Private	4.33	0.47	5.94	.000
	Public	4.05	0.49		
Academic Success	Private	4.14	0.48	7.63	.000
	Public	3.80	0.54		

Note. Significant at $p < .001$.

The result of Independent Samples *t*-test between students from public and private universities is shown as Table 4.11. The results indicate significance for all three variables between the two groups.

The results show that the students at the private universities ($M = 4.18$) had much higher scores than the students at the public universities ($M = 3.68$) for Linguistic Capital, which means that the students at the private universities had higher English language resources.

Likewise, in the case of English Prestige, private university students ($M = 4.33$) expressed much higher levels of prestige of English than public university students ($M = 4.05$).

Similarly, Academic Success was significantly higher for the private university students ($M = 4.14$) than for the public university students ($M = 3.80$). The results indicate that pupils learning at private universities had relatively high academic results compared to those learning in public universities.

Overall, the p-values for all of the three variables were less than 0.001; this meant that the difference between students from the public and private universities observed for all the three variables was statistically significant.

6.2. Link with Research Objective 2

The second research objective aimed to compare the degree of linguistic capital, prestige of English and academic success of students of public and private universities, directly addressed by the Independent Samples t-test. The results clearly showed that the student in the private university who were given to the research proved that they possessed members of all three variables significantly higher than the students in the public university, which is in support of the research objective.

6.3. Answer to Research Question 2

Research Question 2: *How do students from selected public and private sector universities differ in terms of linguistic capital, English prestige, and academic success?*

The results show that students attending private universities have a much higher linguistic capital, a higher perception of prestige of English and better academic success in comparison to the students attending public universities. Thus, for Research Question 2, it is clear that there is a difference between the two university sectors, namely significant institutional differences.

7. Summary of Findings

The statistical analyses give full support to the findings of the relation between linguistic capital, English prestige and academic achievement. The descriptive statistics showed that students' language skills were generally high, they had positive attitudes toward the prestige of English, and their English academic achievements were rather good. Reliability analysis found that the research instrument was very high in internal consistency, meaning that the questionnaire used in the study was appropriate to measure the studied variables.

The first research objective was met with the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis, which yielded positive correlations for all three variables pertaining to the first research question: linguistic capital, prestige of English and academic success. Beyond this, results from the Independent Samples t-test indicated statistically significant differences in the mean scores of public and private university students with the students

from private universities having higher mean scores on all three variables. The second research question was answered by these findings, indicating that the institutional context is important in determining students' linguistic resources, perceptions of the prestige of English and academic success.

In general, the findings confirm the ideas of Bourdieu's Theory of Linguistic Capital, which implies that English is a helpful language asset that improves the educational opportunities and efficacy of the higher education system in Pakistan. The results are explained in the light of the previous literature and theory in the next section.

8. Discussion

This study investigated the correlation between linguistic capital, prestige of English and academic achievement amongst students of selected public and private sector universities of Punjab, Pakistan. The study aimed to find out if there were differences between students studying in public and private universities; whether linguistic capital and perceived prestige of English are related to the academic success of students and whether the differences are significant, based on Bourdieu's (1991) Theory of Linguistic Capital. The results indicated a positive relationship between linguistic capital, prestige of English and academic success, and that students from private universities expressed significantly higher levels of all variables compared to students from public universities. The results are consistent with Bourdieu's theoretical hypothesis and add to the body of empirical studies of sociolinguistic studies in Pakistan.

The first aim of the study was to look at the link between linguistic capital, English prestige and academic achievement among university students. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis showed that the three variables were found to have strong positive correlations. In particular, those who had higher linguistic capital saw the English language as a prestigious language and had better academic performance. The results here show that English is not just a means of communication but is also an effective educational tool which enriches the pupils' learning process and performance.

In sum, these results confirm Bourdieu's (1991) hypothesis that language can serve as symbolic capital that can create educational and social benefits. Bourdieu argues that schooling promotes the reproduction of social inequalities due to its reward for the dominant linguistic variety. English is dominant in Pakistan as a language of higher education, research and professional communication. As a result, English-proficient students are able to better comprehend academic content, engage in class discussions, meet assignment requirements, and access international scholarly literature. This is current evidence that the linguistic capital still plays a significant role in the educational outcomes of the higher education system in Pakistan.

Our results are comparable with the results of previous studies carried out abroad. English has emerged as the major language of higher education and globalization, allowing

students to gain access to international knowledge and jobs opportunities, as argued by Coleman (2011). Similarly, Macaro et al. (2018) found that EMC had a positive effect on academic engagement, comprehension and learning outcomes of students with adequate English proficiency. These conclusions are supported by the positive relationship between linguistic capital and academic outcomes found in the present study which shows that students with more English language capital do better than other students academically.

Likewise, the results are congruent with the results of a study carried out in Pakistan. Rahman (2022) noted that English is an important indicator of educational privilege and socioeconomic mobility, and Shamim (2017) reported that students from English-medium education have fewer academic problems compared to students educated via Urdu or regional languages in universities. The present results support these observations and show the importance of linguistic capital on students' school achievement and confidence in school. The positive correlation between the prestige of English and academic achievement also suggests that students' attitudes affect their motivation to learn English and actively engage in academic activities.

Another significant result of this study is the issue of the prestige of English. Students were found to be very positive about the necessity of English for higher education, for success in the professions and for employment from the descriptive analysis. The results indicate that students have a perception of English not just as a language of school but also as a language of social status and achievement. This view is similar to that of Mahboob (2020), who identified the perception of English in Pakistan that it is linked to intelligence, professionalism, and social mobility to the upper classes. The current study builds upon this literature by showing that positive perceptions of prestige of English are also linked to better academic outcomes.

The second goal of the study was to contrast the linguistic capital, prestige of English and academic success of public school and private school students. The differences between the two sectors were statistically significant (IS t-test). The students who studied in private universities reported more linguistic capital and more positive attitudes toward prestige of English and academic performance than the students from public universities. The findings suggest that institutional context is important in influencing students' language experiences and educational outcomes.

There are a number of possible reasons for this variation. Private universities are more likely to offer English teaching, new teaching methods, digital teaching resources, interactive teaching methods, and communication skills training. Pupils at these schools are additionally likely to have advantages in terms of their linguistic capital, having previously developed in their English-medium education. Many students from public universities, on the other hand, learn their initial education in Urdu or local languages and thus encounter more difficulties to shift to English-medium university education. The

differences in these institutions may account for some differences in the confidence, involvement in class, academic writing, and academic performance of students.

The results of the present study corroborate Bourdieu's (1991) theory that educational institutions are more likely to reward students with the dominant linguistic capital. The students who already have stronger English language skills benefit more from the education provided in English, which dominates education in Pakistan. The impact of preuniversity linguistic capital differences therefore persists in the university environment. The findings indicate that the educational inequalities could be reinforced when the institutions are dependent on English but fail to offer enough language support to students whose first language is not English.

Results also support Rahman (2022) who stated that educational inequity is also caused by unequal access to English education in Pakistan. Similarly, Shamim (2017) pointed out that the background of a language can also impact students' confidence and academic engagement in universities. The present study builds on this work by examining the relationships between language assets and educational outcomes in both public and private universities in order to show that the institutional context is an important factor in shaping students' language assets and educational experiences.

In a theoretical sense, the results enhance the validity of the theory of Linguistic Capital in the Higher Education Sector of Pakistan. The findings show that English is symbolic capital that can provide educational benefits and support students' learning outcomes. English is not just a means of communication, but is also a valuable social resource which affects pupils' education, confidence and career prospects. This reinforces the argument put forward by Bourdieu that there is a close connection between language and power, prestige and social inequality.

In general, the results suggest that the language capital which students possess (and the prestige of English) is of great importance to the students' success in their academic work in Pakistani universities. The positive relationships between study variables and the significant differences among public and private university students indicate that the context of the institution and a language exposure have significant effects on educational outcomes. These findings also enrich sociolinguistic research as it gives empirical evidence that English is still an important linguistic resource in Pakistan's higher education system. They further emphasize the importance of enhancing the English language support programmes, academic writing courses and training in communication skills at the universities, and English language support at the school level for students coming from Urdu or regional language education system. These programs can be used to reduce linguistic inequalities and to improve the equity in academic opportunities provided by public and private universities.

9. Conclusion

The present study focused on the relation of linguistic capital, English prestige and academic success of students of selected universities of Pakistan (Government and Private Sector) in Punjab. Based on the Theory of Linguistic Capital by Bourdieu, the results showed that there was a positive correlation between linguistic capital and students' academic success and prestige of English. The findings also showed that there were significant differences between public and private university students, as the private university students had higher scores in the following areas: linguistic capital, prestige of English and academic performance.

The results show that English still remains a valuable language tool in the context of higher education in Pakistan. The students with better English skills could participate in academic activities, understand content of the courses, complete English-medium tasks, and attain better learning outcomes. Likewise, the high-achiever students had positive perceptions of English, indicating that positive perceptions of English lead to greater academic achievement and hence greater motivation and engagement in education.

Analysis of the comparisons shows that there is a significant role for institutional context in the development of students' linguistic capital and their learning experiences. There seem to be some distinctions between the opportunities available to students in public and private universities for developing a proficiency in English, and for gaining an academic and social advantage from the use of English. The results confirm Bourdieu's thesis that language is a symbolic capital that can produce educational benefits and perpetuate social inequalities.

In general, this study is making contribution to the existing literature by giving empirical evidence from Pakistan that Linguistic capital and English prestige are important factors in determining academic success in Higher Education. The results indicate that a high emphasis needs to be placed on improving support programmes for the English language, academic communication skills, and equitable language policies on campus, especially among students from different language backgrounds when entering universities. Increasing the availability of linguistic resources to ensure equal access to them can contribute to lowering the educational inequalities and improve the academic performance of the public and private sector universities.

10. Recommendations

a) Improve ELSP Programmes: Universities, especially public sector universities, should have comprehensive English language support programmes which involve academic writing workshops, communication skills courses and language laboratories. Such programs can enable students to acquire language capital to prepare them for success in school and minimize language gaps among students with differing educational backgrounds.

b) Language policies in higher education institutions should be such that it provides a balance between the use of English and sufficient academic support to students who have gone through primary and secondary education in Urdu or regional languages. Bridging courses and foundation programmes need to be established to support students' entry to higher education in English.

c) Recommendations for future studies: Studies in linguistic capital and English prestige should be conducted in a wide range of universities from across the provinces of Pakistan based on mixed methods or longitudinal designs. Other factors in the analysis can also be considered, including socioeconomic status, parental education, language attitudes, and employability, to better understand what factors affect academic success.

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